

Spectrophotometric Determination of Nitrite in Water

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A new method has been investigated for the determination of nitrite in potable and polluted water, based on the reaction of nitrite with *p*-aminoacetophenone in acid medium to form diazonium salt which is coupled with *N*-(1-naphthyl)ethylenediamine dihydrochloride to give an intense purple coloured dye. The dye shows absorption maxima at 545 nm. The molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity being $4.6 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $0.0010 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ respectively. The other analytical parameters and application of the method for analysis of polluted water have been investigated. Copper and iron which interfere with other methods do not interfere upto a reasonable amount.

INADEQUATELY treated effluents of various industries add to the contamination of nitrite in water. The presence of nitrite in water is harmful as it causes methemoglobinemia and forms carcinogenic nitrosoamine when present with secondary or tertiary amines^{1,2}. It also affects the dissolved oxygen content of water. The maximum permissible limit as fixed by U.S. Public Health Association is 0.06 ppm in potable water³.

Many analytical methods have been proposed for the spectrophotometric determination of nitrite in polluted water. Most of these are based on Griess reaction⁴⁻⁸, i.e. the formation of a dye by diazotisation of an aromatic amine with nitrite and coupling of azo compound with an aromatic amine or phenol. Many of these methods have good sensitivity and selectivity but require close control of pH and temperature during diazotisation step as well as a relatively long coupling time. Here, a new reagent system using *p*-aminoacetophenone and *N*-(1-naphthyl)ethylenediamine has been used for the determination of nitrite in ppm level. In this spectrophotometric method *p*-aminoacetophenone is diazotised with nitrite and coupled with *N*-(1-naphthyl)ethylenediamine (NEDA) in acid medium to give a purple colour dye showing maximum absorbance at 545 nm. The proposed method is free from the interference of Cu^{II} and Fe^{III} which are normal interferents in other methods⁹⁻¹¹ and has been successfully applied for the analysis of nitrite in polluted water and is comparable to the standard method using sulphanilamide and NEDA¹⁴ in sensitivity.

The colour reaction involves two steps. In the first step, *p*-aminoacetophenone reacts with nitrite ion to form acetophenondiazonium chloride and in second step, with *N*-(1-naphthyl)ethylenediamine dihydrochloride to give purple coloured azo dye having $\lambda_{\text{max}} = 545 \text{ nm}$.

Experimental

All spectral studies were made with a ECIL GS-865 spectrophotometer and a Carl-Zeiss Spokol using 1 cm matched glass cells.

A stock solution of sodium nitrite was prepared by dissolving 150 mg of dried analytical grade reagent in 100 ml of demineralised water. A little chloroform was added as a stabiliser¹². The working standard (1 mg NO_2^- per ml) was prepared by appropriate dilution of the stock solution.

A 1% solution of *p*-aminoacetophenone (AAP) was prepared in hydrochloric acid (1:4). A 0.1% (w/v) aqueous solution of *N*-(1-naphthyl)ethylenediamine dihydrochloride (NEDA) was prepared. Solutions of foreign ions were prepared by the method of West¹⁴.

All chemicals used were of AnalaR grade.

Procedure: An aliquot of sample solution containing nitrite (2.5–20 μg) was taken in a 25 ml volumetric flask. To it *p*-aminoacetophenone solution (1 ml) was added and allowed to stand for 2 min to ensure complete diazotisation. Then 0.1% solution of NEDA (2 ml) was added for coupling, kept for 2 min and then the volume made upto the mark with 6 *M* hydrochloric acid. The absorbance of purple coloured dye formed was measured at 545 nm against the reagent blank after 5 min. The calibration curve from 2.5 to 20 μg of nitrite per 25 ml of the solution was prepared in a similar manner.

Results and Discussion

The dye shows maximum absorption at 545 nm while the reagent blank shows negligible absorption at this wavelength. The dye is stable for 30 h.

Effect of varying reaction conditions: The effect of acidity, time, etc. on the diazotisation was

studied. It was found that 1 M of hydrochloric acid was sufficient for complete diazotisation. The time necessary for complete diazotisation was ~1 min. The absorbance was constant for development period of 1–90 min. The diazotisation reaction was fast at room temperature. It was observed that stability and the intensity of the coloured dye was constant when the final volume was made upto the mark with 6 M hydrochloric acid after the addition of NEDA. The effect of varying molar ratios of *p*-aminoacetophenone (*p*-APP) and NEDA were studied. For *p*-APP and nitrite, the absorbance was constant for molar ratios of 1 : 1.

Beer's law, molar absorptivity, sensitivity and reproducibility : Beer's law is obeyed in the range 2.5–20.0 $\mu\text{g NO}_2$ per 25 ml (0.1–0.8 ppm). The molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity were found to be $4.60 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $0.001 \text{ } \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$, respectively.

The reproducibility of the method was checked by taking replicate analysis of standard nitrite solution (10 $\mu\text{g}/25 \text{ ml}$) over a period of 7 days. The standard deviation and relative standard deviation were found to be 0.007 and 1.75%, respectively.

TABLE 1—REPRODUCIBILITY OF THE METHOD

Concentration of nitrite = 10 $\mu\text{g}/25 \text{ ml}$

Sample no.	Absorbance (1 = 545 nm)
1.	0.400
2.	0.395
3.	0.390
4.	0.410
5.	0.395
6.	0.410
7.	0.400
Mean = 0.400	
Standard deviation = 0.007	
Relative standard deviation = 1.75%	

Effect of foreign ions : In order to assess the applicability of the method, the effect of foreign ions commonly present in water was studied. For this purpose, known amounts of foreign ions were added to a solution containing 10 μg of nitrite per 25 ml. Cu^{II} and Fe^{III} do not interfere upto 7 and 40 ppm, respectively. The interference due to SO_2 was masked with H_2O_2 . The tolerance limits (ppm) of foreign ions and compounds are as follows : Cu^{II} (7) ; phenol, aniline and formaldehyde (40), Li^{I} , Be^{II} , Mo^{VI} , W^{VI} , Sb^{III} , Se^{IV} , Al^{III} , Cr^{VI} and fluoride (100) ; Mg^{II} , Ca^{II} , Sr^{II} , Ba^{II} , Zr^{IV} , Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Zn^{II} (150) ; nitrate, phosphite, bicarbonate and sulphate (800) ; tartarate and EDTA (1000) ; Bi^{III} (80) ; Fe^{III} (40), 1 ml sodium potassium tartarate as masking agent ; sulphite and sulphur dioxide (10), 1 ml of 1% H_2O_2 solution as masking agent.

Application of the method to polluted water : In order to check the validity of the method for the analysis of nitrite in polluted water, two series

of experiments were carried out. In the first experiment, the amount of sample solution taken was varied and diluted to a constant volume by deionised water. For all the samples the estimation of nitrite in polluted water was quantitative. In second experiment, recovery of nitrite was checked by adding various amounts of nitrite to the sample solutions. The results obtained were linear and identical with those of calibration graph obtained with deionised water.

Samples were collected from different points from the source of industrial effluents and preserved by the addition of mercuric chloride and stored at 0°C . The samples were analysed by the proposed method as well as by the standard method using sulphanilamide–NEDA method. The data is given in Tables 2 and 3, which show that the proposed method is comparable to the standard method in sensitivity.

TABLE 2—DETERMINATION OF NITRITE IN TAP WATER*

Sample no.	Nitrite added ($\mu\text{g}/25 \text{ ml}$)	Nitrite found proposed method ($\mu\text{g}/25 \text{ ml}$)	Recovery %	Nitrite found standard method ($\mu\text{g}/25 \text{ ml}$)	Recovery %
1.	2.0	2.0	100.0	2.0	100.0
2.	4.0	4.1	101.7	4.0	100.0
3.	6.0	5.9	97.5	6.0	100.0
4.	8.0	8.0	100.0	7.9	98.0
5.	10.0	10.0	100.0	10.0	100.0

* Normal tap water gave no test for nitrite.

TABLE 3—DETERMINATION OF NITRITE IN POLLUTED WATER

Sample no.	Concentration of nitrite (ppm)	
	Proposed method	Standard method
1.	0.34	0.33
2.	0.36	0.37
3.	0.46	0.46
4.	0.52	0.53
5.	0.66	0.65
6.	0.71	0.73
7.	0.69	0.68
8.	0.78	0.78

* First 4 samples are from upstream and the remaining 4 from downstream of the effluent source.

The method is sensitive and free from the interference of Cu^{II} and Fe^{III} and successfully applied for the analysis of nitrite in polluted water.

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